

Notes

Manganese (III) Complexes of Tridentate Schiff Bases

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(Manuscript received 8 March 1972; revised 13 November 1972; accepted 14 November 1972)

RECENTLY some Schiff bases have been used to stabilize manganese(III) ion as the metal chelates¹⁻⁸. We have now isolated a manganese (III) complex of the dibasic tridentate Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and *o*-aminophenol (SOAP-H₂), the preparation and properties of which are described here.

Experimental

Manganese(III) acetate dihydrate was prepared by a previously published method⁹. All the solvents and chemicals were purified and dried by standard methods. The molar conductance, electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility were measured and elemental analyses were performed as described previously⁷.

Preparation of the Mn(III)-Schiff base complex: The red complex was prepared by refluxing (3 hr) an equimolar mixture of the Schiff base and manganese (III) acetate dihydrate in dry methanol. The precipitated complex was filtered off, washed with methanol and dry diethylether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. (Found: Mn, 16.23; N, 4.35; C, 52.72; H, 5.12%; calc. for [Mn(SOAP)(CH₃COO)(H₂O)] : Mn, 15.99; N, 4.08; C, 52.50; H, 4.08%). $\Lambda_M = 5.3$ ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ (conc. $1.8 \times 10^{-3} M$ in acetonitrile); $\mu_{eff} = 4.85$ B.M. (23°C); ν_{max} at 22,500 cm⁻¹ (log $\epsilon \approx 3.5$) and at 17,300 cm⁻¹ (log $\epsilon \approx 2.7$) (in methanol); I.R. spectral data are set out in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The dry complex is quite stable for handling in the laboratory. Elemental analyses of the compound correspond to the formula [Mn(SOAP)(CH₃COO)(H₂O)] (where, SOAP-H₂ = a molecule of the dibasic tridentate Schiff base) and its paramagnetic moment of 4.85 B.M. is fairly close to the spin-only value for high-spin d⁴ system. It is moderately soluble in methanol and acetonitrile and is practically non-conducting in acetonitrile. The molar conductance value supports the coordination of acetate ion, which is further substantiated by infrared spectral data (Table 1). The coordination of water molecule is also supported by infrared spectral results. The

[infrared bands at 3500, 930 and 830 cm⁻¹ demonstrate the presence of coordinated water molecule (possibly with hydrogen bonded with the neighbouring molecule^{10,11}). The bands at 1552 and 1450 cm⁻¹ are due to the asymmetric and symmetric COO⁻ stretching frequency respectively in the complex.

TABLE I. I.R. SPECTRAL DATA (IN KBr DISK) OF [Mn(III)(SOAP)(CH₃COO)(H₂O)]

Band (cm ⁻¹)	Intensity	Probable assignments
3500	medium & broad	Coordinated and hydrogen bonded water molecule.
3000-2500	weak multiple bands	C-H stretch
1614	very strong	C = N stretch
1600	strong	C = C stretch
1552	medium	C = C in plane vibration mixed up with asymmetric COO ⁻ stretch.
1480	very strong	C-H deformation of C-CH ₃ group.
1455	shoulder	not assigned
1450	strong	symmetric COO stretch
1380	medium	C-H deformation
1325	weak	not assigned
1300	very strong	phenolic C-O stretch
1295	shoulder	not assigned
1255	medium	not assigned
1225	medium	C-N stretch
1170-1150	two medium bands	not assigned
1130-1045	two weak bands	1 : 2 disubstitution
970	weak	not assigned
930	medium	coordinated water molecule
850	weak & broad	not assigned
830	strong	coordinated water molecule
750	very strong, doublet	C-H out-of-plane deformation and 1 : 2 disubstitution; 4-adjacent free H-atoms.

The difference of 102 cm⁻¹ between the two bands and their positions indicate symmetrical bidentate nature of the acetato group¹⁰. The C = N and phenolic C-O stretching frequencies in the free ligand are observed at 1633 and 1278 cm⁻¹ respectively. These two bands in the Mn(III) complex have been shifted to 1614 and 1300 cm⁻¹ respectively. The lowering of the C = N stretching frequency is an indication of the coordination of imine nitrogen atom and thus indicating less double-bond character in the C = N bond¹². The shift of phenolic C-O to higher frequency in the complex is possibly due to the change of hydrogen bonded structure to covalent metal bonded structure¹². Tentative assignments of the other important bands are included in Table 1.

The electronic spectra of the Mn(III) complex in methanol show two bands, one at 22,500 cm⁻¹ (log $\epsilon \approx 3.5$) and the other broad band at 17,300 cm⁻¹ (log $\epsilon \approx 2.7$). Usually the high-spin Mn(III) complexes¹³ with octahedral geometry give one charge

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transfer band around $25,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\log \epsilon \approx 3.5$) and a spin-allowed d-d transition band, ${}^5E_g \rightarrow {}^5T_{2g}$ around $20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\log \epsilon \approx 2.5$). The high energy band observed in this compound may be considered as a charge transfer band, while the band at $17,300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to d-d transition. This broad band, occurring at lower frequency with increased intensity, indicates the lowering of symmetry of the complex from the regular octahedral geometry.

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Separation of Metal E.D.T.A. Complex Ions by Paper Electrophoresis*

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(Manuscript received 17 April 1970; revised 28 August 1971; accepted 9 February 1972)

A NUMBER of workers¹⁻³ have used electromigration in paper to separate EDTA complex ions of some metals. The present communication deals with the electrophoretic migration of some water soluble E.D.T.A. complexes using paper as supporting medium and separation of a few binary mixtures of ions in $0.05M$ disodium salt of E.D.T.A. carrier electrolyte.

To prepare water-soluble complexes of Cu(II), Pb(II), Bi(III), Cd(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), TiO(II), Hg(II), UO₂(II), VO(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Tl(I) ions using Na₂-E.D.T.A. as a ligand freshly prepared metallic oxides or hydroxides were treated with $0.05M$ Na₂ E.D.T.A.; the solutions obtained were filtered from the excess oxides or hydroxides as the cases were and subjected to paper electrophoresis using $0.05M$ Na₂ E.D.T.A. as carrier electrolyte.

Durrums type⁴ vertical and Wieland and Fischer type⁵ horizontal electrophoretic sets were used for the present investigation. For the separation of anionic species horizontal type of apparatus was helpful as the negatively charged mixed ions could be applied at the cathode end of the paper strip thus increasing the possibility of the separation of these ions, due to increased length of migration. After electrophoresis the electropherograms were developed with suitable reagents and from the direction of migration it could be said that except Tl(I) and Ag(I) ions all the above mentioned ions formed stable anionic complexes. Tl(I) ion under this condition does not form stable anionic complex which is evident from its migration towards the cathode.

In order to observe whether anionic complexes of the above mentioned ions and also those of Ag(I), and UO₂(II) ions are formed during electrophoresis using $0.05M$ Na₂ E.D.T.A. as carrier electrolyte, simple salt solutions of these ions without prior complex formation were applied. It was found that Tl(I) ion under these conditions migrated to the cathode proving thereby its existence as cation while other ions moved to the anode as the complex MYⁿ⁻⁴ ion (where M is metal ion, n the charge on the metal ion, H₄Y. the ligand E.D.T.A.). Ag practically remained at the point of application.

TABLE I. SEPARATION OF BINARY MIXTURES OF IONS MIGRATING IN OPPOSITE DIRECTION

mixture	Time of run = 3 hr Potential gradient = 5.88 volts/cm		
	Distances of migration of the migrants		
	"+"	"0"	"-"
PbY ⁻² -Tl(I)	PbY ⁻² 3.7 cm		Tl(I) 6.2 cm
FeY ⁻² -Tl(I)	FeY ⁻² 2.1 cm		Tl(I) 6.1 cm
UO ₂ Y ⁻² -Tl(I)	UO ₂ Y ⁻² 3.8 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm
HgY ⁻² -Tl(I)	HgY ⁻² 4.9 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm
CuY ⁻² -Tl(I)	CuY ⁻² 3.7 cm		Tl(I) 6.2 cm
NiY ⁻² -Tl(I)	NiY ⁻² 3.2 cm		Tl(I) 6.1 cm
CrY ⁻² -Tl(I)	CrY ⁻² 4.8 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm
CoY ⁻² -Tl(I)	CoY ⁻² 3.4 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm
BiY ⁻² -Tl(I)	BiY ⁻² 4.9 cm		Tl(I) 6.2 cm
VOY ⁻² -Tl(I)	VOY ⁻² 4.7 cm		Tl(I) 6.2 cm
TiOY ⁻² -Tl(I)	TiOY ⁻² 5.2 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm

Due to these differences in the directions of migration and differential rates of movement of simple as well as complex ions, successful separations of a few binary and ternary mixtures of the above ions by paper electrophoresis using $0.05M$ Na₂ E.D.T.A. as carrier electrolyte, have been achieved.

* Read at the 57th Session of the Indian Science Congress, 1970.